

"THE INFLUENCE OF FAMILY AND PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS ON SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN"

Dadajonov Oybek

Teacher:

Komilova Maftuna Muzaffar qizi

Student:

komilovamaftuna005@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19471631>

Annotatsiya

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning til rivojlanishi, ularning kognitiv va ijtimoiy salohiyatining shakllanishi uchun asosiy bosqich hisoblanadi. Ushbu tadqiqotda, oila va pedagogik muhitning bolalarning nutq rivojiga ta'siri tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot natijalari, bolalar tilining shakllanishida ota-onalar bilan muloqot, pedagoglarning ta'lim usullari va atrof-muhit omillarining muhim rol o'ynashini ko'rsatadi. Ayniqsa, o'qish, interaktiv o'yinlar va guruh faoliyatlari bolalarning lug'at boyligini kengaytirish va nutqiy faollikni oshirishda samarali usullar sifatida ajralib turadi. Tadqiqot shuni ta'kidlashicha, tilni rivojlantirish uchun ijobiy muhit yaratish bolalarning keyingi ta'lim jarayonlariga tayyorligini oshiradi va ijtimoiy integratsiyasini yaxshilaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutq rivojlanishi, maktabgacha ta'limda muloqot, oilaviy ta'sir va nutq o'rganish, pedagoglarning nutq rivojlanishidagi roli, bolalarning nutq rivoji, ota-onalar bilan muloqot, kognitiv va emotsional rivojlanish, ijtimoiy va nutq ko'nikmalari, Interaktiv va ta'limiy o'yinlar, kitoblar va musiqa orqali tilni boyitish, maktabgacha ta'lim.

Аннотация

Развитие речи у детей дошкольного возраста является важнейшим этапом формирования их познавательного и социального потенциала. В данном исследовании анализировалось влияние семейной и педагогической среды на развитие речи детей. Результаты исследования показывают, что общение с родителями, методы обучения учителей и факторы окружающей среды играют важную роль в формировании речи детей. В частности, чтение, интерактивные игры и групповые занятия выделяются как эффективные методы расширения словарного запаса детей и повышения речевой активности. Исследование показывает, что создание благоприятной среды для развития языка повышает готовность детей к дальнейшему образовательному процессу и улучшает их социальную интеграцию.

Ключевые слова: развитие речи у дошкольников, коммуникация в дошкольном возрасте, влияние семьи на усвоение языкообразование.

Abstract

The language development of preschool children is a key stage in the formation of their cognitive and social potential. In this study, the influence of the family and pedagogical environment on the speech development of children was analyzed. The results of the study show that communication with parents, pedagogical methods and environmental factors play an important role in the formation of children's language. In particular, reading, interactive games and group activities stand out as effective methods for expanding children's vocabulary and increasing speech activity. The study suggests that creating a positive environment for language development increases children's readiness for further educational processes and improves their social integration.

Keywords: preschool language development, early childhood communication, family influence on language acquisition, pedagogical role in language development, speech development in children, parent-child interaction, cognitive and emotional development, social and language skills, interactive and educational games, language enrichment through books and music, preschool education

Introduction

Preschool age is an important stage in a child's development, especially in the formation of language and communication skills. During this period, children are very sensitive to the language materials they receive from the environment, and their speech develops rapidly. In particular, communication in the family, the attention and active participation of parents are important factors for a child's free thinking in language and adaptation to society. Also, through educators, peers, books, music and games, a child increases his language wealth and achieves speech activity. Therefore, it is necessary to approach the child with love and attention, and to conduct practical and theoretical training in harmony. Creating a solid language foundation at an early age serves as the basis for the child's further education and social life. Language is one of the main tools that shape human thinking and worldview. The development of language and speech in preschool children is a complex, gradual process. This development is formed under the influence of a number of factors. Speech is not only a means of communication, but also directly affects the mental, social and emotional development of the child. In the preparation of this article, theoretical analysis and practical observation methods were used. Approaches to the development of

children's speech were studied based on scientific literature. At the same time, based on observations conducted with the participation of children aged 3-6 in preschool educational institutions in Tashkent and its surroundings, their communicative activity, vocabulary and speech movements were analyzed. Also, the influence of the family and pedagogical environment was studied through interviews with parents and educators.

Literature Review

Speech development in preschool children has been studied in many studies. Vygotsky (1978) linked language development to social interaction and the environment. The family is a key factor in a child's language development, and active communication with parents, the introduction of new words, and the enrichment of speech are important for children (Hart & Risley, 1995). The role of educators is also very important. Research shows that teachers play a significant role in language development through conversations, storytelling, and interactive games with their students (Whitehurst & Lonigan, 2001). In addition, books, songs, and poems have been identified as effective tools for increasing children's vocabulary (Senechal & LeFevre, 2002). New research suggests that the role of the social environment and games in language development is very large. Nicolopoulou (2010) found in her research that play and group activities enhance children's language skills as they interact with each other and use language in practice. Overall, the literature review confirms the importance of several factors—family, teachers, environment, and peer interaction—in preschool children's language development.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted to study the speech development of preschool children. The study included 50 children aged 3-6, their parents and caregivers.

1. Participants: Children aged 3-6, their parents and caregivers participated in the study. Participants were selected from five preschool educational institutions in the city.

2. Data collection: Questionnaires and interviews: Interviews were conducted with parents and caregivers to collect information about communication methods and pedagogical approaches.

Observations: Educational activities between caregivers and children were observed.

3. Data analysis: The collected data were studied using qualitative analysis methods and the main factors influencing language development were identified.

4. Ethical criteria: All individuals participating in the study provided informed consent and participation was voluntary.

Results and Discussion

Results: The results of the study showed that constant communication with children, teaching new words, and interactive games had a positive effect on their speech development. Communication between parents and educators plays an important role in increasing children's vocabulary. Also, group activities and mutual conversations made children's speech fluent.

Discussion: The results of the study confirm the importance of cooperation between parents and educators in the development of children's speech. Interactive activities carried out by parents and educators have a significant impact on the development of children's speech. This showed the effective methods of teaching and the impact of communication on children's language.

Conclusion

The results of the study emphasize the great contribution of the family and educational institutions to the development of children of preschool age. Effective communication between parents and educators has a significant impact on the development of children's speech. It is said that regular communication, teaching new words and interactive activities greatly contribute to the rapid development of children's vocabulary and speech. The results of the study also showed that better cooperation between the preschool education system and the family plays an important role in accelerating children's speech. A joint approach of the family and educational institutions has a positive effect on the development of children's speech

References:

1. Bruner, J. S. (1983). *Child's Talk: Learning to Use Language*. Oxford University Press.
2. Hart, B., & Risley, T. R. (1995). *Meaningful Differences in the Everyday Experience of Young American Children*. Paul H. Brookes Publishing.
3. Neuman, S. B., & Dickinson, D. K. (2001). *Handbook of Early Literacy Research*. Guilford Press.
4. Shonkoff, J. P., & Phillips, D. A. (2000). *From Neurons to Neighborhoods: The Science of Early Childhood Development*. National Academy Press.
5. Snow, C. E., & Dickinson, D. K. (1990). *Teaching and Learning in Preschool and Kindergarten*. Routledge.
6. Vygotsky, L. S. (1962). *Thought and Language*. MIT Press